

27 July 2023

Re: RFI Response: Roadmap for TIP

To: Dr. Chaitan Baru
2415 Eisenhower Ave
Alexandria, VA 22314, USA
TIPRoadmap-RFI@nsf.gov

From: Organization: Executive Board, Long Term Ecological Research Network (lternet.edu)
Type: Academic Research Network

Thank you for the opportunity to provide input to inform the development of a roadmap for the TIP Directorate. This response provides suggestions from the Executive Board of the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) Network. Funded by the NSF, the LTER Network has over 2000 scientists from a broad range of environmental and social science disciplines who conduct long-term research to understand how ecological systems function over decades. For more than 40 years, LTER investigators distributed across 27 sites that span forest, desert, grassland, agricultural, urban, coastal, marine, and polar ecosystems have developed and tested fundamental ecological theory, established seminal ecosystem experiments, advanced predictive modeling, developed best practices for ecological information management, and innovatively trained the next generation of ecological scientists. In addition, sustained engagement of large teams of scientists from academia, governmental, and non-governmental sectors with resource managers, policymakers, educators, and public audiences has enabled the LTER Network to guide decisions that benefit the environment and society (Fig. 1). For this reason, we are eager to engage with the TIP Directorate in cultivating the training, tools, and partnerships required to solve the world's most pressing environmental challenges.

The Environmental and Ecological Sciences have had an extraordinarily strong record of diagnosing problems, proposing solutions to those problems, working effectively across the science/society interface to have those solutions implemented, and then conducting research and monitoring to track the success of those solutions. The recovery of iconic species such as the Bald Eagle, marked improvements in air quality issues such as acid rain, improvements in eutrophication of lakes, rivers, and estuaries, and the development of advanced conservation strategies for a dynamically changing world are all examples of successful solutions-based research in the Environmental and Ecological Sciences that are highly relevant to the mission of the new TIP directorate. And these Sciences are evolving in impressive ways. Recent LTER research in urban settings has acknowledged the primacy of technology and the built environment, promoting a social-ecological-technical systems (SETS) approach to long-term ecological research. The LTER Network has the capacity to contribute more substantially to transformative solutions for a more sustainable and resilient future for the entire biosphere. We note that much of our success has been coincident with improvements in diversity, equity, and inclusion, especially for women within our discipline.

In this response, we urge the TIP Directorate to consider four principles across five of the key focal and challenge areas that are essential for designing, engineering, and managing the structure and function of SETS for a more resilient and sustainable future.

1. *Projects with the potential to result in cost savings should be valued equally with projects that have the potential to generate new earnings. That principle should be clearly articulated in TIP solicitations and in the review process.*

This principle is essential for addressing climate change and environmental sustainability (challenge area #4). It is the basis for the programs like the World Bank Group Global Program on Sustainability that promotes the measurement and valuation of *natural capital* – the planetary resources and ecosystem services necessary to sustain economies. In particular, the nation’s role in global climate mitigation will depend on urgently needed improvements to the US carbon capture and storage market, including through implementation of nature-based approaches. Such improvements will rely heavily on data from the geo- and environmental sciences, including land cover maps from remotely sensed imagery and ground-based measurements of carbon fluxes and stocks. For example, LTER research in agricultural systems has shown that different cropping systems can result in markedly different greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration, information that is necessary to implementing carbon markets in agricultural systems. Scalability will depend on an expanded footprint of carbon stock and flux data and investments in scientific collaborations that improve the quantification methods and technologies for monitoring, reporting, and verifying greenhouse gas emissions and emission reductions data linked to national and international registries. These include modeling approaches to forecast carbon stocks and fluxes under alternative climate change scenarios. An expansion of interdisciplinarity programs that foster collaborations among ecologists, social scientists, and economists is essential for developing carbon currencies, projecting market potential, and advancing technologies and practices to increase carbon retention or storage.

2. *TIP should consider approaches to funding that support effective government and non-profit partnerships alongside industry partnerships. The past structure of funding instruments has excluded not only industry partners, but also, to a large degree, government and non-profit partners.*

Engagement of partners across sectors is an important pillar of TIP and will be necessary for enacting decisions about natural capital such as carbon (described above) but also for understanding natural and anthropogenic disasters (focus area #5). Long-term observational and experimental research has been particularly adept at revealing the causes and consequences of disruptions, including resilience mechanisms across ecosystems that vary in degrees of local to global human disturbance. Scientists engaged in long-term studies have substantial expertise in environmental sensing, multidimensional data processing and interpretation, and modeling – technology that

with TIP investment, could be expanded in capacity, efficiency, and distribution to improve the nation's capacity to more comprehensively sense and predict the impact of disasters. Expanded opportunities for engagement in translational science through partnerships that extend across public and private sectors are necessary to ensure discoveries are incorporated into decisions that enhance resilience of ecosystems and their services as they are confronted by rapid change. For example, studies at coastal LTER sites underscore the critical role natural ecosystems play in mitigating the effects of tropical storms and hurricanes – discoveries that scientists are eager to ensure are successfully incorporated into disaster prevention and mitigation through transdisciplinary partnerships with decision makers.

3. *Industry and government partners should be held to the same standards of data and research transparency as academics when funded under TIP. Citizens are paying for the research and are entitled to share in the resulting benefits. Re-use of data for new questions and initiatives is becoming standard, and the data resulting from TIP funding stands to be immensely valuable in both commercial and public sector efforts.*

This recommendation targets focus area #8, advancing data storage and management. The LTER Network has played a major role in advancements to ecoinformatics that underlie Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles of data management. FAIR principles have catalyzed major advancements in all domains of science, including cross-ecosystem synthesis in the LTER Network, but even more critically, have promoted environmental literacy and informed decision-making by their use by decision-makers, educators, and the general public. Relating to recommendations 1 and 2, above, LTER expertise in information management could help inform creation of a national database that promotes a more nimble carbon market that could adjust stock estimates after disasters or when new information is available – a critical tool for an effective carbon market but one that is wholly dependent on adherence to FAIR principles by data providers.

4. *TIP should invest in industry and academic research partnerships that result in patents for technologies that revolutionize the scale of research accessibility through cost-reduction of instrumentation. Investing in strategic, large-scale testing of new low-cost technologies could generate revenue for further research and development as well as provide expanded access to tools and data for scientists and students that could enhance equity of the underserved.*

There is ample evidence that addressing TIP challenge areas #3 (workforce development and skill gaps) and #5 (inequitable access to education, opportunity, or other services) is fundamental to providing solutions to social-ecological challenges. This recognition underlies the LTER Network's longstanding dedication to cultivating durable relationships among individuals, local and regional communities, and minority-serving institutions (Fig. 1), prioritizing leadership opportunities for early career scientists including investigators from historically excluded groups. However, major obstacles to

equitable engagement in science remain, including accessibility of instrumentation and training in big data collection and interpretation. The LTER community strongly advocates that the TIP Directorate consider investing in the development of low-cost technologies that would dismantle financial barriers and accelerate solutions-oriented data collection and integration by connecting scientists from diverse backgrounds across the environmental and engineering disciplines.

We hope that these suggestions help the Directorate create a roadmap that cultivates long-term partnerships among academics and other sectors necessary for sustaining a fragile biosphere.

Figure 1. A partial list of long-standing LTER partners across industry, governmental, non-profit, and educational sectors that ensure data and discoveries serve public needs.

Industry Partners:

Aquatic Research South; Arborjet, Inc; Lakes Region Community Developers; Lyme Timber Company; Northland Forest Products; Resilient Buildings Group; Sustainable Futures Consulting; Twin Pines Housing Trust; Illumina; EcoLandMod, Inc; Assessment Payers Association of the Middle Rio Grande; Hilcorp

Nonprofit Partners:

National: Joint Genome Institute; UNAVCO; Natural Areas Association; Smithsonian Environmental Research Center; The Nature Conservancy; National Audubon Society; National Tropical Botanical Gardens; ARCUS; Ocean Conservancy; Lenfest Ocean Program; PolarTrec; The Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation; Atitla Center

State and Local (examples): Museum of the White Mountains; Building Community in NH; New England Forestry Foundation; Northern Woodlands; Squam Lakes Natural Science Center; Denver Botanic Garden; Colorado Forest Restoration Institute; Museum of Boulder; Cal-Wood Academy; Nature Kids Lafayette/Jovenes de la Naturaleza; Winter Wildlands Alliance; Bonefish and Tarpon Trust; Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon; Sanibel-Captiva Conservation Foundation; Everglades Foundation; New Mexico Natural Heritage Program; Rio Grande Water Fund; Massachusetts Museum of Contemporary Art; Friends of Cooper Island; Market Road Films; Coastal Futures Conservancy; Pollock Conservation Cooperative Research Center; Essex County Greenbelt; Gulf of Maine Institute; Parker-Ipswich-Essex River Restoration; Trustees of Reservations; Mississippi Park Connection; McDowell Sonoran Conservancy; Barrier Islands Center; SouthWings; One People One Reef

Government Partners:

Federal: USGS; NOAA; NASA; National Park Service; Cooperative Ecosystem Study Unit; USFWS; USDA Forest Service; Department of Energy; US EPA; NRCS; National Weather Service; US Army Corps of Engineers; US Bureau of Reclamation; Department of Homeland Security; Naval Research Laboratory; National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency

Government Partners (cont.)

State and Local: GA Department of Natural Resources; NH Housing Authority; City of Boulder Watershed; Rocky Mountain National Park; South Florida Water Management District; Everglades National Park; Albuquerque Bernalillo County Water Utility Authority; NM Game and Fish; New Mexico Department of Agriculture; Pueblos of Isleta, Sandia, Santa Ana, and Santo Domingo; City of Albuquerque Fire Department; Alaska Fisheries Science Center; City of Kaktovik; Ukpavvik Inupiat Corporation Science; City of St Paul, Department of Parks and Recreation, Department of Public Works; Mississippi Watershed Management Organization; Riley Purgatory Bluff Creek Watershed District; Three Rivers Park District; Washington Conservation District; Minnesota GreenCorps - Minnesota Pollution Control Agency

Schools and School Districts:

Miami-Dade County Public Schools; The Bosque School; North Slope Borough School District; Battle Creek Public Schools; Centreville Public Schools; Vicksburg Community Schools; Comstock Public Schools; Delton Public Schools; Detroit Public Schools; Gull Lake Community Schools; Harper Creek Community Schools; Kalamazoo Public Schools; Lawton Community Schools; Accomack Co. Public Schools; Northampton County Public Schools

